

Table 1. Recommendations and preventive actions for the early stage.

Concept: Recommendation				
Symptom	No.	Name	Attribute	Value
Experiencing increased trouble with planning or organizing.	1	RMI1	DescriptionRecommendation	Use visual reminders.
			Examples	Wall calendar, weekly planner.
	2	RMI2	DescriptionRecommendation	Consider using more permanent reminders for tasks the person does regularly.
			Examples	A note by the door to remember their keys and wallet.
	3	RMI3	DescriptionRecommendation	Use visual clues that explain where items go.
			Examples	Photos with words on cupboard doors, pictures
Getting lost	4	RMI4	DescriptionRecommendation	Encourage movement and exercise.
			Examples	Gardening, weeding, or pruning, or a more strenuous activity like raking or mowing grass. Indoor bowls skittles, Dance Seated exercises, Swimming, Walking, Tai chi, or qigong.
	5	RMI5	DescriptionRecommendation	Maintain regular routines.
			Examples	
	6	RMI6	DescriptionRecommendation	Remove visual reminders from sight.
			Examples	Coat, purse, hat,glasses.
	7	RMI7	DescriptionRecommendation	Involve or redirect her attention with an activity.
			Examples	Reading books, newspapers or magazines or audio books or podcasts. Visiting friends or family members. Looking at old photographs or souvenirs from past events. Cooking together. Puzzles. Flower arranging. Listening to favorite music.
	8	RMI8	DescriptionRecommendation	Help her connect with familiar items and objects.
			Examples	Photos, personal items.
	9	RMI9	DescriptionRecommendation	Try a barrier like a curtain or colored streamer to mask the door.
			Examples	A “stop” sign or “do not enter” sign also may help.
	10	RMI10	DescriptionRecommendation	Place a black mat or paint a black space on your front porch.
			Examples	
	11	RMI11	DescriptionRecommendation	Add “child-safe” plastic covers to doorknobs.
			Examples	
	12	RMI12	DescriptionRecommendation	Have your relative wear an ID bracelet and sew ID labels in their clothes.
			Examples	

	13	RMI13	DescriptionRecommendation	Tell neighbors about your relative's wandering behavior and make sure they have your phone number.
			Examples	
Loosing things or misplacing them	14	RMI14	DescriptionRecommendation	Label drawers and cabinets where you keep everyday articles with large printed signs.
			Examples	
	15	RMI15	DescriptionRecommendation	Limit the number of hiding places.
			Examples	Locking rooms, closets, and drawers that are not regularly used.
	16	RMI16	DescriptionRecommendation	Important or valuable items can be kept out of sight or locked up.
			Examples	Medications.
	17	RMI17	DescriptionRecommendation	Designate special storage places for items.
			Examples	Keys, eyeglasses, hearing aids and batteries, dentures, and other essentials.
	18	RMI18	DescriptionRecommendation	Learn the person's hiding places.
			Examples	Favorite hiding places for gifts.
19	RMI19	DescriptionRecommendation	Check trash baskets before you empty them.	
		Examples		
Mood and personality changes	20	RMI5	DescriptionRecommendation	Maintain regular routines.
			Examples	
	21	RMI7	DescriptionRecommendation	Involve or redirect her attention with an activity.
			Examples	Reading books, newspapers or magazines or audio books or podcasts. Visiting friends or family members. Looking at old photographs or souvenirs from past events. Cooking together. Puzzles. Flower arranging. Listening to favorite music.
	22	RMI20	DescriptionRecommendation	Make him feel valued and productive.
			Examples	
	23	RMI21	DescriptionRecommendation	Be ready to help him start an activity.
			Examples	
	24	RMI22	DescriptionRecommendation	Make her with dementia feel included in groups.
			Examples	
25	RMI23	DescriptionRecommendation	Counselling, cognitive behavioural therapy, and group therapy may be helpful.	
		Examples		
26	RMI24	DescriptionRecommendation	Antidepressant medications may help. Talk to the person's doctor about the options.	
		Examples		
Repeating questions	27	RMI7	DescriptionRecommendation	Involve or redirect her attention with an activity.
			Examples	Reading books, newspapers or magazines or audio books or podcasts.

				Visiting friends or family members. Looking at old photographs or souvenirs from past events. Cooking together. Puzzles. Flower arranging. Listening to favorite music.
	28	RMI25	DescriptionRecommendation	Repeat your answer once or twice and then try to change the subject.
			Examples	
	29	RMI26	DescriptionRecommendation	Respond to the emotions rather than to the words.
			Examples	
	30	RMI27	DescriptionRecommendation	Keep your answers brief.
			Examples	
	31	RMI28	DescriptionRecommendation	Speak calmly and answer the question like the first time
			Examples	
Trouble handling money and paying bills	32	RMI29	DescriptionRecommendation	Remove all credit cards from the person's wallet.
			Examples	
	33	RMI30	DescriptionRecommendation	Fill the person's wallet with photographs, a small amount of money, identification cards.
			Examples	
	34	RMI31	DescriptionRecommendation	If the patient wants to pay the cashier in a store, hand her the correct change.
			Examples	

Table 2. Recommendations and preventive actions for the moderate stage.

Concept: Recommendation				
Symptom	No.	Name	Attribute	Value
Changes in sleep patterns	1	RMI4	DescriptionRecommendation	Encourage movement and exercise.
			Examples	Gardening, weeding or pruning, or a more strenuous activity like raking or mowing grass. Indoor bowls skittles, Dance Seated exercises, Swimming, Walking, Tai chi or qigong.
	2	RMI5	DescriptionRecommendation	Maintain regular routines.
			Examples	
	3	RMO1	DescriptionRecommendation	Help her to avoid naps if the person has trouble sleeping at night.
			Examples	
	4	RMO2	DescriptionRecommendation	Evaluate any physical or emotional problems that may be contributing to sleep difficulties, such as pain or depression.

			Examples	
	5	RMO3	DescriptionRecommendation	Restrict sweets and avoid caffeine at night.
			Examples	
	6	RMO4	DescriptionRecommendation	Have the person use the toilet before going to bed.
			Examples	
	7	RMO5	DescriptionRecommendation	Consult a doctor or pharmacist if you suspect the person's medication may be contributing to a problem with sleeping.
			Examples	
Sundowning	8	RMI4	DescriptionRecommendation	Encourage movement and exercise.
			Examples	Gardening, weeding or pruning, or a more strenuous activity like raking or mowing grass. Indoor bowls skittles, Dance Seated exercises, Swimming, Walking, Tai chi or qigong.
	9	RMO3	DescriptionRecommendation	Restrict sweets and avoid caffeine at night.
			Examples	
	10	RMO6	DescriptionRecommendation	Stay nearby while she's doing the task so that you can reassure her.
			Examples	
	11	RMO7	DescriptionRecommendation	Encourage a nap after lunch, if it does not interfere with sleeping at night.
			Examples	
	12	RMO8	DescriptionRecommendation	Make "quiet time" with soft music after lunch part of your routine.
			Examples	
	13	RMO9	DescriptionRecommendation	Have an early dinner or late afternoon snack.
			Examples	
	14	RMO10	DescriptionRecommendation	Good lighting can sometimes assist in reducing confusion. Reducing noise and excess stimulation.
			Examples	
15	RMO11	DescriptionRecommendation	Telling her the time, where she is, and what is going on can also help decrease confusion and anxiety.	
		Examples		
16	RMO12	DescriptionRecommendation	Redirect her attention with an activity.	
		Examples		
17	RMO13	DescriptionRecommendation	Close the curtains or blinds at dusk to minimize shadows and the confusion they may cause.	
		Examples		
18	RMO14	DescriptionRecommendation	Provide items of comfort.	
		Examples		
Delusion and paranoia	19	RMO12	DescriptionRecommendation	Redirect her attention with an activity.
			Examples	
	20	RMO15	DescriptionRecommendation	Leave her alone or approach her slowly to avoid scaring her.

			Examples	
	21	RMO16	DescriptionRecommendation	Avoid arguing or trying to explain that what she is thinking, seeing, or hearing is not real.
			Examples	
	22	RMO17	DescriptionRecommendation	Covering or removing mirrors and patterned carpets or wallpaper that may be confusing the person.
			Examples	
	23	RMO18	DescriptionRecommendation	Check for noises that the person could confuse with someone speaking.
			Examples	
	24	RMO19	DescriptionRecommendation	Make sure the person has had recent hearing and sight tests. Any glasses or hearing aids should be in good condition and working well.
			Examples	
	25	RMO20	DescriptionRecommendation	If their hallucinations involve multiple senses get immediate medical advice.
			Examples	
Repetitive behavior	26	RMO12	DescriptionRecommendation	Redirect her attention with an activity
			Examples	
	27	RMO21	DescriptionRecommendation	Ask yourself, Who does the behaviour bother? If it isn't bothering anyone else, do nothing.
			Examples	
	28	RMO22	DescriptionRecommendation	Give him something to occupy his hands.
			Examples	
	29	RMO23	DescriptionRecommendation	Consult with staff to see if you can fit the repetitive action into household chores.
			Examples	
Difficulty in doing tasks involving multiple steps	30	RMO24	DescriptionRecommendation	Match the activity with what the person with Alzheimer's can do.
			Examples	
	31	RMO25	DescriptionRecommendation	Choose activities that can be fun for everyone.
			Examples	
	32	RMO26	DescriptionRecommendation	Help the person get started.
			Examples	
	33	RMO27	DescriptionRecommendation	Decide if he or she can do the activity alone or needs help.
			Examples	
	34	RMO28	DescriptionRecommendation	Watch to see if the person gets frustrated.
			Examples	
	35	RMO29	DescriptionRecommendation	Make sure he or she feels successful and has fun.
			Examples	
	36	RMO30	DescriptionRecommendation	Let him or her watch if that is more enjoyable.
			Examples	
Confusion about where they are or what day it is.	37	RMO31	DescriptionRecommendation	Mark a calendar with the date.
			Examples	

	38	RMO32	DescriptionRecommendation	Buy a daily newspaper.
			Examples	

Table 3. Recommendations and preventive actions for the severe stage.

Concepto: Recommendation				
Symptom	No.	Name	Attribute	Value
Seizure	1	RS1	DescriptionRecommendation	Keep the patient safe and comfort.
			Examples	
	2	RS2	DescriptionRecommendation	Place something soft under the patient's head.
			Examples	
	3	RS3	DescriptionRecommendation	Remove glasses.
			Examples	
	4	RS4	DescriptionRecommendation	Move any heave or sharp objects out of the way.
			Examples	Chair, tables.
	5	RS5	DescriptionRecommendation	Lay the patient on their side.
			Examples	
	6	RS6	DescriptionRecommendation	Call a service emergency if the patient is injured or the seizure lasts more than two minutes.
			Examples	
Weight loss	7	RS7	DescriptionRecommendation	Avoid food out of schedule.
			Examples	
	8	RS8	DescriptionRecommendation	Ensure patient's dentures are properly fitted.
			Examples	
	9	RS9	DescriptionRecommendation	The eating area should be quiet and calm.
			Examples	
	10	RS10	DescriptionRecommendation	Serve meals at the same time.
			Examples	
	11	RS11	DescriptionRecommendation	The patient's weight should not lose less than 5kg monthly.
			Examples	
Difficult to walk or sit	12	RS12	DescriptionRecommendation	Change the patient's position in bed.
			Examples	
	13	RS13	DescriptionRecommendation	Do range-of motion exercises to prevent stiffness and pressure sores.
			Examples	
	14	RS14	DescriptionRecommendation	A physical therapist can show you how to transfer the person safely.
			Examples	
15	RS15	DescriptionRecommendation	Could be a sign of pain or a sign of discomfort. Check for ill.	

Groaning moaning or grunting	16	RS16	Examples	
			DescriptionRecommendation	Check which situations reduce this behavior and try to expand this situation.
	17	RS17	Examples	Talking with the patient, giving her-his a hand rub or engaging her-giving her-his a hand rub,listening to music.
			DescriptionRecommendation	The patient was called to attention by calling her first name and then was directed to take a deep breath and count to 10.
Increased sleeping	18	RS18	Examples	
			DescriptionRecommendation	It may also be worth asking for a medication review with the General practitioner or speaking to a pharmacist as medication can cause a range of side effects.
	19	RS19	Examples	
			DescriptionRecommendation	If the person is sleeping a lot but it isn't having a negative impact on them it is often best to just go with it and make sure they are comfortable.
Inability to recognize oneself or family	20	RS20	DescriptionRecommendation	If you sense he doesn't recall your name or who you are remind Him.
			Examples	
	21	RS21	DescriptionRecommendation	Show older pictures of family and friends to reminisce together.
			Examples	
	22	RS22	DescriptionRecommendation	If the patient is anxious or worried you can try to change the subject or sing a favorite song with him.
			Examples	
	23	RS23	DescriptionRecommendation	Validation Therapy.
			Examples	If the patient continually refers to you as her/his father - ask her/his to tell you about her/his dad- what she/he misses about him. Give her/his the opportunity to share her/his memories of him
Difficulty swallowing	24	RS24	DescriptionRecommendation	Encourage the person to feed themselves as much as possible during meals.
			Examples	
	25	RS25	DescriptionRecommendation	Give the patient enough time to chew and swallow each mouthful.
			Examples	
	26	RS26	DescriptionRecommendation	During the meal and for at least 20 minutes after the meal the patient should be seated in an upright position.
			Examples	
	27	RS27	DescriptionRecommendation	Say "swallow" to remind him or her to swallow.
			Examples	
	28	RS28	DescriptionRecommendation	Find out if the person's pills can be crushed or taken in another form.
			Examples	
	29	RS29	DescriptionRecommendation	Offer drinks of different temperatures to see which might be easiest for the person to drink.
			Examples	
30	RS30	DescriptionRecommendation	Avoid use a straw instead have the person drink small sips from a cup.	

			Examples	
	31	RS31	DescriptionRecommendation	Grind or blend food to make it easier to eat.
			Examples	
	32	RS32	DescriptionRecommendation	Make sure to cut food into small pieces and that it is soft enough for the person to eat.
			Examples	
	33	RS33	DescriptionRecommendation	Offer soft foods.
			Examples	Bananas, sweet potatoes, mashed avocado, applesauce, yogurt.
Lack of control of bowel and bladder	34	RS34	DescriptionRecommendation	Choose clothes with fastenings that the person can undo easily when using the toilet.
			Examples	
	35	RS35	DescriptionRecommendation	Keep track of bowel movements in order to learn the person's patterns.
			Examples	
	36	RS36	DescriptionRecommendation	Make it easier for the person to find their way to the toilet.
			Examples	
	37	RS37	DescriptionRecommendation	Put a sign on the toilet or bathroom door.
			Examples	
	38	RS38	DescriptionRecommendation	Keep the genital area clean and dry to avoid infections and discomfort.
			Examples	
39	RS39	DescriptionRecommendation	Praise independence and regular use of the bathroom; do not punish or shame for episodes of incontinence.	
		Examples		
40	RS40	DescriptionRecommendation	Establish a regular toileting routine every 2-3 hours.	
		Examples	Upon rising, before and after meals, and at bedtime.	
Skin infection	41	RS41	DescriptionRecommendation	Loose clothing made of soft fabric reduces friction and pressure on the person's skin.
			Examples	
	42	RS42	DescriptionRecommendation	Check for rashes and sores.
			Examples	
	43	RS43	DescriptionRecommendation	Gentle cleaning.
			Examples	
	44	RS44	DescriptionRecommendation	Encourage daily exercise
			Examples	Stand up and move about regularly, sit unsupported for a few minutes each day, Lie as flat as possible on the bed for 20-30 minutes each day, Balance in a standing position, In the sitting position shuffle along the edge of the bed from one end of the bed to the other.
	45	RS45	DescriptionRecommendation	Use of protective aids.
			Examples	Soft cushions, waterbeds, sheepskin bed pad, or an "egg-crate" foam mattress pad.

	46	RS46	DescriptionRecommendation	Move someone's position at regular enough intervals to reducing skin pressure.
			Examples	
	47	RS47	DescriptionRecommendation	Use pillows or pads to protect bony areas.
			Examples	
	48	RS48	DescriptionRecommendation	Keep skin clean and dry.
			Examples	
Inability to communicate	49	RS49	DescriptionRecommendation	Don't rush – allow plenty of time and look for non-verbal clues from the person.
			Examples	
	50	RS50	DescriptionRecommendation	Even if you don't think the person understands or is listening keep talking to them.
			Examples	
	51	RS51	DescriptionRecommendation	Talk about things the person finds interesting or from their past.
			Examples	
	52	RS52	DescriptionRecommendation	Consider responding to them in the way they respond to you.
			Examples	Gestures, Sounds.
	53	RS53	DescriptionRecommendation	Touching the person's hand.
			Examples	
	54	RS54	DescriptionRecommendation	Use positive body language.
			Examples	Smiling, Facial expressions.
55	RS55	DescriptionRecommendation	Keep eye contact when communicating.	
		Examples		